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READING CULTURE IN MODERN LIFE OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the author conducts a comparative analysis of printed and electronic books. Drawing on the results of sociological surveys carried out in various countries, the author emphasizes the advantages of paper publications as a traditional reading medium. Despite the clear benefits of e-books, such as ease of use, compactness, and relative cost-effectiveness, attention is drawn to their drawbacks - particularly their negative impact on eyesight and the reduced level of aesthetic appreciation. In conclusion, the author formulates possible solutions to the identified problem.

Key words: reading culture, library, reading, survey, computer addiction, internet, book, support of reading culture, youth of Uzbekistan.

Ashrapov Ravil Ramzaevich

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O'ZBEKISTONNING ZAMONAVIY HAYOTIDA KITOBXONLIK MADANIYATI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada muallif bosma va elektron kitoblarning qiyosiy tahlilini amalga oshirar ekan, turli mamlakatlarda o'tkazilgan sotsiologik so'rovlar natijalariga ko'ra, qog'oz nashrlarning an'anaviy o'qish vositasi sifatidagi afzalliklari ta'kidlangan. Elektron kitoblarning foydalanish qulayligi, ixchamligi va nisbatan tejamkorligi kabi yaqqol afzalliklariga qaramay, ularning salbiy tomonlariga - xususan, ko'rishga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi va estetik idrok etish darajasining pasayishiga e'tibor qaratiladi. Xulosa qilib aytganda, muallif aniqlangan muammoning mumkin bo'lgan yechimlarini shakllantiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: kitobxonlik madaniyati, kutubxona, kitobxonlik, so'rovnoma, kompyuterga qaramlik, internet, kitob, kitobxonlik madaniyatini qo'llab-quvvatlash, O'zbekiston yoshlari.

Ашрапов Равиль Рамзаевич

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КУЛЬТУРА ЧТЕНИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЖИЗНИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье автор проводит сравнительный анализ печатных и электронных книг, подчеркивая преимущества бумажных изданий как традиционного средства чтения на основе результатов социологических опросов, проведенных в различных странах. Несмотря на очевидные преимущества электронных книг, такие как удобство использования, компактность и относительная экономичность, внимание акцентируется на их негативных аспектах - в частности, отрицательном влиянии на зрение и снижении уровня эстетического восприятия. В заключение автор формулирует возможные решения выявленной проблемы.

Ключевые слова: культура чтения, чтение, опрос, компьютерная зависимость, интернет, книга, поддержка читательской культуры, молодежь Узбекистана.

Introduction and relevance of the topic. In an era of large-scale digitalization of society and global economic, political and social transformations in our country, reading culture is becoming one of the most important and key means of acquiring new knowledge, improving education, increasing cultural experience and socializing young people, and therefore requires serious and sustained support.

The decline in interest in reading is seen as a destructive phenomenon in society and gives grounds to assert that there is a systemic decline in the culture of reading. A dismissive attitude towards the problem of reading could lead the global community to a point of no return, beyond which the degradation of society could follow.

The culture of reading is the main tool for the socialization of young people, a way of acquiring the values, ideas and norms of modern society. People who read are distinguished by their ability to relate to real life, to be prepared for all unpredictable situations, to grasp the whole picture instantly, to have a large amount of long-term memory, and to solve all problematic issues creatively. Reading helps people develop their speech faster, making it more expressive and expanding their vocabulary. People who read are sociable, independent in their behavior, internally free, and self-critical. Consequently, reading, general literacy, culture, and education are important conditions necessary for the social adaptation and active participation of young people.

Young people, especially schoolchildren, have begun to turn more to computer and phone games, social networks, and other multimedia sources that do not require mental effort, rather than books. This problem is not limited to a single country, but affects the entire world, the entire planet. In addition to serious efforts by the state and institutional systems, a way out of this situation requires: "... instilling reading skills and habits as key educational competencies and, moreover, a love of reading as a vital necessity, which depends primarily on the family and school, which are the most important social institutions" [1].

In order to study this trend, remedy the situation and take measures to address this issue, book scholars, educators, librarians, publishers, writers and politicians have been consulted.

Methods and level of study. The research methods used in the study include such scientific methods as social surveys, questionnaires, and content analysis.

Librarians and bookshop employees were the first to feel the decline in reading activity when they noticed an outflow of readers from libraries and an unabated number of books on dusty bookshelves. They were the first to raise the question of the crisis in book production and paper reading at the end of the twentieth century, concerned about the information technology revolution in reading and competition from the global Internet. "It was librarians who noticed that modern youth had changed their tastes in reading philosophy: previously, they chose books where they could empathize with the main characters and feel negative towards the negative characters, but now their choice of books leans more towards fun, games and entertainment" [2].

In world science, the problems of researching reading culture can be found in the works of Plato, Socrates, Aristotle, and Descartes. The topic of reading has been studied particularly deeply and seriously by contemporary foreign scholars: M. McLuhan, D. Barton, and S. Fischer. A. Manguel, E. Bertels, A. Compagnon, A. Gaben, V. Bartold, J. Sartre, M. Hamilton, R. Chartier and many others. The study of reading culture and book science has been proposed in the most famous works of Russian scientists of the 19th and 20th centuries: N. Lisovsky, M. Kufaev, N. Rubakin, E. Nemirovsky, E. Katsprzhak, and the scientific works of contemporary CIS researchers: A. Reitblat, A. Belovitskaya, E. Melnikova, Yu. Melentyeva, N. Seliverstova, T. Galaktionova, E. Russkikh, M. Gudova, V. Borodina, Scholars, linguists and researchers of reading culture in Central Asia: A. Karlybekova (Kazakhstan), A. Yazberdyev (Turkmenistan), A. Tagirdzhanov, B. Gafurov (Tajikistan).

Issues of spiritual and moral education of young people and the importance of its improvement, reading culture and its development in Uzbekistan are deeply covered in the works of book scholars and historians of modern Uzbekistan, such as: E. Rtveladze, E. Akhunjanov, Sh. Kushokov, N. Safarova, A. Umarov, V. Livshits, A. Abdulazizov, Sh. Kamoliddin, N. Khabibullaev, M. Iskhakov, K. Khanazarov, D. Ganieva and many others.

E. Akhundzhanov offered an original opinion, explaining how handwritten books lost their place to printed books on the book market: “It is not only that demand for handwritten books is falling due to their relative expensiveness compared to printed books. Another important factor in the disappearance of handwritten books from the historical scene was the fact that they were always created as unique author’s copies and works of special book art, but by the beginning of the 20th century, in the changed social conditions, they had lost their customers — true connoisseurs and lovers who had existed on a massive scale in previous centuries” [3].

Manuscript books, as one of the main sources of spiritual life in Turkestan and as a form of intellectual continuity between generations, played a very important role. And despite the importance and value of the function that handwritten books performed for society and the state, having lost their readers (admirers), they gave way to printed books, which were more economical and convenient to use. “Has the time now come for printed books to give way to electronic, ‘screen’ books? Was Martin Luther right when he declared that ‘printing is the last and greatest gift of God’” [4].

Discussion. It is worth mentioning here how many books are published in the world, so much so that it sometimes seems that there are more writers than readers. As the aphorism goes: “In the past, there were few books and many people seeking salvation. Now there are many books, but who can say how to find salvation?” [5] Bookstore shelves are full of dusty and often unclaimed books. Isn’t one of the reasons for the decline in the authority and devaluation of book production the “diversity of one-day books” [6], the huge number of (sometimes) expensive books about nothing? In our opinion, a writer, an author, must feel his reader.

As N. A. Rubakin wrote, there should be an organic connection between the author and the reader; “each writer has their own group of readers, their own audience, and each type of reader has their own set of authors” [7].

V. G. Belinsky shared the same opinion: “Writers who do not know the people, their character, their customs, their way of life, or their needs should not write books for the people” [8].

But here’s what’s interesting: despite the rapid and widespread entry of electronic media into our lives, and the fact that many sources of information (books, magazines, periodicals) have moved to the Internet thanks to digitalization, survey data from the last ten to fifteen years show that young people still consider paper books to be the main source of information (knowledge).

How and why can this be explained? After all, the whole world claims the opposite, that children and young people are no longer reading paper books, increasingly turning to electronic media?

Let’s try to understand this issue.

In November 2020, the Uzreport television channel, in collaboration with the Youth Union of Uzbekistan, conducted a survey of 1,500 respondents from across the country. The aim of the study was to find out whether young people in Uzbekistan read books, to ascertain their preferences, which authors they read, what format they prefer to read in, and so on.

When asked, ‘How often do they read books?’, it turned out that 22% of young people do not read books at all.

Diagram No. 1

For comparison, we took data from a survey of young people in Russia, one of the most reading countries in the world, France and Germany, the most developed countries in Europe.

According to data from ‘Social survey’, one in three young people under the age of 35 in Russia does not read books. This is about thirty-three percent of the population. In France, reading one book a month is considered the norm for high school students. According to data from the German Reading Society, young people in Germany spend only 9 minutes a day reading books, while watching television for about 135 minutes. [9]

In Uzbekistan, as can be seen from Diagram No. 1, the percentage of young people who read is 78%.

Diagram No. 2

As shown in Diagram No 2, printed books remain the most popular choice among electronic (screen), printed (book) and audiobooks in Uzbekistan, accounting for 77% of the market. 19% of participants aged between fourteen and twenty-four preferred electronic books. Audiobooks were preferred by 4% of young people.

Continuing the comparative analysis of reading culture, it is worth noting that in 2007, in studies by A. Umarov and A. Abdulazizov [10], the following answers were received to a similar question: ‘What sources do you use to obtain knowledge?’:

- books – 79.2%;
- newspapers and magazines – 10.8%;
- the Internet – 2.2%;
- television, radio – 3.8%;

-various tests – 5%; [10]

As we can see from the survey results, the use of books has remained at approximately the same level after 10-15 years – young readers in Uzbekistan still prefer printed materials.

Another study conducted by Russian librarians in 2021 is equally important. Respondents (library readers) were asked the question: ‘What sources of information do you prefer?’ They were asked to choose from six options. (Diagram No. 3). The respondents’ answers were distributed as follows: 85% answered that books are their main source of information; 55% of respondents prefer to obtain information on the Internet; 38% use electronic media; 38% are satisfied with information obtained from newspapers and magazines; 7% identified television and radio broadcasts as their main sources; 2% of respondents named archival materials as their main sources of information. [11]

Rating of use of information sources

Diagram No. 3

Results. As can be seen from the above data, young people still prefer printed (paper) books.

“A. Oreshina writes in her dissertation that for many people, books have become “a familiar object in the space around us”. For this object – the book – to function, the reader must perform certain actions: pick it up, open it, and flip through its pages. Compared to an e-book, a real book can be felt, seen, touched, and compared with other books in terms of weight. It can be evaluated by smelling a new (old) book, turning its pages, and carrying it around. Unlike a virtual, intangible substance, a physical book accompanies a person throughout their life and bears the mark of its owner-reader – notes in the margins, dedications, torn pages, dog-eared corners used as bookmarks” [12].

It is important for a person to feel a book, interact with it, and relate to it emotionally. Sometimes a book is the most faithful and devoted friend in difficult times. All this tangible richness is missing in electronic readers.

As O. Mandelstam wrote about the process of reading a paper book: “I read Pallas with shortness of breath, without rushing. <...> Pallas’s bright and voluminous book is printed on dry Chinese paper. Its pages are wide and grainy. Reading this naturalist has a wonderful effect on the disposition of the senses, straightens the eyes and communicates a mineral quartz calm to the soul” [13].

R. Bradbury, in his novel *Fahrenheit 451*, writes that a book is like “a white dove, fluttering its wings, obediently descending into your hands. The open page glimmers in the dim light, like a snow-white feather with a pattern of words inscribed on it” [14].

It is optimistic that young people are not indifferent to the fate of printed resources, promising them their rightful and deserved place in the future. Society, young people, and readers are aware of the need to form a new culture of reading, where printed products can coexist with electronic

publications and sources. This means that traditional books have not yet lost their readers. They are still needed! They are in demand!

Continuing the theme of the socialization of the younger generation in society and the protection of paper books, it must be said that computer and telephone addiction has in turn led to another psychological addiction – fubbing – the constant habit of people being distracted by their phones, even when talking to someone else. According to scientific research, people look at their phones every 5-8 minutes on average per day. That is an average of 100-150 times. Along with this, new phobias have emerged as side effects – nomophobia, the fear of losing one’s phone, and FOMO (fear of missing out) – the fear of not knowing what others know.

It should be noted that prolonged use of electronic devices (tablets, laptops, computers, gadgets) and exposure to electromagnetic radiation have a negative impact on our nervous, immune, endocrine and reproductive systems. It also has a negative effect on the musculoskeletal system and vision – prolonged sitting causes the muscles of the body to atrophy, the nervous system to become depleted, and the body to become more vulnerable to numerous psychosomatic illnesses. As a result of such prolonged work in front of electronic screens, headaches, redness and watery eyes, ‘sand’ under the eyelids, accommodation disorders, double vision, pain in the neck and collar area, dizziness, nausea and, ultimately, due to prolonged fatigue, exhaustion of the body. This fairly common phenomenon among young people has been dubbed ‘computer vision syndrome’.

Doctors in Denmark, after studying occupational diseases among computer users, concluded that working with a computer mouse for many hours is harmful to the ligaments and muscles of the hand. After studying nearly 7,000 computer workers from 11 Danish companies over two years, the doctors compared those who used the mouse frequently with those who used it infrequently. It turned out that working with a mouse for more than thirty hours a week, which is about 4-5 hours a day, leads to pain in the right shoulder, right side of the neck and the computer user’s working hand eight times more often than in people who do not sit at work for more than one hour a day. Designers, engineers, computer artists, and gamers are at risk.

According to Anne Mangen, a professor at the University of Stavanger in Norway, e-books will never be able to replace traditional paper books. According to the results of numerous experiments conducted by Anne Mangen herself and many other scientists, e-books are inferior to real, ‘living’ books in many respects and will continue to be so. When reading a paper book, the brain creates a so-called ‘mental map’ of the book and the work being read, consisting of direct contact with the book, tactile sensations, the appearance of the book itself, its thickness, hardness, the smell of printing ink, the place where the book was read, returning to the page and line where reading was interrupted for some reason, and the story of how it came into the reader’s hands. When reading a paper book, the ‘architecture’ of the work appears, a sense of the volume of the book, the mental ability to ‘walk’ through the pages. “A faceless e-book with a single screen fragment does not have such ‘anchors’ and what has been read remains in the memory as something lifeless, disorderly, chaotic and unstructured, where only the main idea of the work is remembered” [15].

These data once again show the premature nature of celebrating the victory of electronic media over book resources.

Conclusions and proposals. The intelligentsia and the country’s leadership are beginning to understand that the knowledge gained through traditional education is insufficient for a spiritual and moral renaissance. It is very difficult to raise such a well-rounded, cultured and educated person without books. Therefore, reading books is at the heart of the education and training of the younger generation – at school, in the library, in the family. But it is impossible to educate solely through books, since each person is individual and unique. But it is unwise to educate and teach young people without books, because books contain centuries of wisdom and the vast knowledge of all the peoples of the world. To rely on books means to follow the example of the main characters, not to repeat their mistakes, to save your energy and time. In a word, to develop. The emotional and intellectual spheres of high school students are still developing, and their needs are not yet fully formed. Young people who are just embarking on the path to adulthood should be inspired by the example of their elders – parents, teachers, and responsible social and government workers.

The youth of Uzbekistan possess a level of intellectual activity and health that sets them apart from other segments of the population: as a labour force, as an intellectual resource, and as the population group most adaptable to new conditions.

Economic sectors and government agencies must be provided with qualified young personnel, which in turn also requires efforts on the part of civil society institutions and especially the state.

We are faced with the task of developing an algorithm for overcoming negative trends in the decline of reading culture. Reading is a vital act, and literature is one of the spiritual tools for moving towards discovering oneself in the real trials of life [16].

The concept of reading culture is that the development of a harmonious personality occurs through education and independent work on oneself, which is impossible without the process of reading. On the other hand, the phenomenon of reading culture itself is formed thanks to the development of the reading process and is directly proportional to the state of society itself.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the phenomenon of 'reading culture' is seen as an inseparable link between external culture and a person's inner world, their upbringing, past experiences, and worldview. Readers cannot be separated from their connection to the world in which they live, think, and communicate. People are an integral part of this world. The phenomenon of reading culture is an indicator of the level of development of a given society (for example, the level of literacy of the population) and a catalyst that stimulates and accelerates the development of social processes.

- Reading culture is a complex, dynamic and complicated formation of the individual and society, determined by spiritual and cognitive needs, which transform the individual into a personality.

- The concept of 'reading culture' consists of several components that make up its multifaceted integrity. These are culture, the history of the emergence and development of books, reading, reading literacy, and writing. The study of these components contributes to a deep and multifaceted study of the phenomenon of reading culture.

- Reading culture, including human culture, personal qualities (especially spiritual ones), society, age characteristics, and human aspirations, presupposes, first and foremost, a principled and serious attitude towards reading, because real reading, whether of a paper or electronic book, changes a person.

- Reading culture is a system conditioned by social influence and the personal, individual characteristics of the person themselves. This system includes: a) the reader (as an open and developing unit of society); b) the level of culture in society; c) support from state institutions (libraries, educational institutions, local authorities); d) the influence of family and school; e) the media (television, the internet, verbal texts). In short, it is an information culture that indirectly interacts with and influences people.

- Underestimating the role of reading culture in any society, whether developed or developing, will inevitably affect the dynamic and, in particular, the substantive aspects of the development of society itself. Society is a living organism that develops dialectically according to its own specific laws. The universal frenzied technologization of society without 'looking' into the future and considering the consequences can lead to irreversible and tragic events, such as the appalling ecological state of the planet, wars, famine and epidemics.

Based on the results of the study, the author put forward the following proposals and recommendations:

1. The discipline "Fundamentals of Reading Culture" should be included in the curriculum of higher education institutions.

2. Every year, schools and universities should hold clubs on reading culture and speed-reading techniques.

3. In primary school, intensive work should be done with children who are lagging behind in learning to read. In the first grades, create a special teaching staff that will be directly involved only

in teaching reading, since reading is the most important tool for mastering and assimilating other subjects.

4. In the upper grades, introduce lessons on reading culture, “The Basics of Reading Culture”.

5. Hold a competition for the best children’s book among writers and poets in the region, city, and districts.

6. Hold a competition among programmers for the best educational computer development (application) for children to improve reading culture.

7. School teachers and university lecturers should develop methodological aids for developing and improving the reading skills of schoolchildren.

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МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁ РЕНЕССАНСИ ЖУРНАЛИ

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AL-9224104729 “JADIDCHILIK TA’LIMOTI MILLIY STRATEGIK G‘OYALARINI OMMALASHTIRISHNING KONSTRUKTIV TRANSDITSIPLINAR MODELINI YARATISH” AMALIY LOYIHASI ASOSIDA TAYYORLANDI.

ПОДГОТОВЛЕНО В РАМКАХ ПРИКЛАДНОГО ПРОЕКТА AL-9224104729 “СОЗДАНИЕ КОНСТРУКТИВНОЙ ТРАНСДИСЦИПЛИНАРНОЙ МОДЕЛИ ПОПУЛЯРИЗАЦИИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКИХ ИДЕЙ ДЖАДИДИЗМА”.

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